

Improving the Service Aspects of the Theory of Population Income Formation

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Abstract: The article reveals the theoretical aspects of the formation of the basic income of the population, the factors influencing it, presents the dual characteristics of the income of the population. A statistical analysis is carried out on them, the level of income of the population in the long term and the level of real wages are assessed.

Key words: income of the population, income structure, real income, savings, financial behavior, savings strategies, households.

Introduction.

Increasing population income to reduce poverty is one of the priority goals in developing the fundamental foundations of the economy. Similarly, the economic development goals of New Uzbekistan are aimed at raising people's income levels to improve their standard of living. In recent years, extensive reforms have been implemented to increase population income and provide additional income opportunities. These include offering various economic and financial benefits, vocational training, and skills enhancement programs.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated, "It is necessary to ensure that people have access to high labor incomes, create wide opportunities for their creative and professional growth, and establish social mobility. At the core of all our efforts lies one goal: to ensure that citizens' real incomes and wages grow faster than the rate of inflation." From this perspective, population income, its formation, and opportunities for growth have become extremely urgent issues, especially in the context of the ongoing pandemic.

Degree of study

The economic essence of population income and its identification is directly related to the need for a unified and comprehensive approach in its interpretation. This is closely connected with the objective determination of the development of economic theory and practice.

Table 1. Systematization of Concepts Related to population income ¹

Scientific Views	The Concept of population income	Authors
In terms of quantity	Population income is: a) The amount of money required to meet its needs.	F. Boe, V.G. Zolotogorov, D.K. Kukushkin, P. Fon Lippe, A.A. Poduzov, Dj. Xiks, I. Fisher
	b) The total monetary income received from all sources over a specific period of time.	A.N. Ananov, E.F. Borisov, M.A. Vinokurov, N.A. Gorelov, I.V. Ilin, Yu.P. Kokin, L.N. Likova, A. Marshall, V.D. Nordxaus, B.A. Rayzberg, P.V. Savchenko, P.A. Samuzlson, A.V. Suvorov, E.A. Ulyanova i dr.

¹ Author's work

	c) The share of the national income created in society.	A.G. Gryaznova, V.M. Kadikov a, I.A. Kurbatova, I.P. Nikolaeva, E.F. Solodovnikova, A.E. Surinov
In terms of quality	Population income refers to the relationships associated with the appropriation, use, and distribution of the created goods within society and among its elements.	D.B. Kadirov, A.E. Surinov

The economic essence of population income begins with the understanding that income has a dual nature. Its source of formation is social production, and the value created by labor. However, ultimately, income is generated as a result of distribution. Distribution relations are primarily related to property relations, as these relations manifest through the prism of appropriation. The different levels of appropriation then determine the amount of population income.

According to Prof. Sh. Shodmonov, “population income refers to the amount of money and in-kind receipts received by them during a certain period (for example, one year)” [2].

A. O‘lmasov and A. Vahobov provide the following definition: “population income refers to the amount of money and in-kind receipts received by them during a certain period (for example, one year)” [4].

X. S. Mukhitdinov studied the link between increasing the standard of living and the socio-economic development of regions, emphasizing the importance of the service sector in improving the standard of living. The standard of living of the population is understood as the level of provision of people with essential material and spiritual goods, as well as the degree to which their consumption and needs are satisfied [5].

According to B.K. G‘oyibnazarov, unlike nominal income, the composition of household disposable income only includes the portion of income that can be used for personal consumption of goods and services, as well as for savings [6].

As noted by Khojiyev, in our country, household income is an important economic indicator because it determines the scope of household consumption, as well as the future deferral of savings and investments [7].

According to Rajabov N. and Uralov B., “population income exists in both nominal and real forms. Nominal income is the income received in cash form. Real income is the nominal cash income adjusted according to the consumer price index for the current period” [8].

Research Methodology

In carrying out this research, methods commonly used in scientific research methodology were employed. Deductive and inductive methods, as well as abstract-logical thinking, were used in studying the trends of changes in household income within the development of the green economy. A systematic analysis was applied in this context. During the scientific analysis process, these research methods were extensively used, particularly in observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, and analysis, with synthesis and analytical methods being widely applied.

Analysis and results

In economic theory and practice, there is still no unified approach to understanding the economic concept of household income. The definition of income, which was developed by economists and statisticians in the 20th century, has undergone significant changes. A logical-theoretical analysis of the views of local and foreign economists on the nature of household income has identified two approaches (see the table):

1. Quantitative approach, in which the external characteristics of income are presented and its quantitative appearance is revealed;

2. Qualitative approach, in which income is characterized as economic relations within society. These approaches contain a one-sided description of household income and do not fully and objectively reveal its essence. In a two-sided approach to household income, we can see that, depending on its characteristics, it is diverse (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Characteristics Derived from the Two-Sided Description of population income ²

In our opinion, the economic essence of population income refers to the economic relations developed between the population and enterprises, the population and the state, and between groups of people and individuals in the process of distribution and redistribution of newly created value. These relations are manifested in the form of the monetary result of income.

The proposed interpretation of the economic essence of population income eliminates a one-sided approach to defining it. First, it provides a single interpretation, second, it establishes the subjects of economic relations, and third, it reveals their quantitative result.

To explain the essence of population income, in addition to the well-known reproductive, status, and incentive functions in economics, the social, regulatory, and accounting functions, which are organically inherent in population income, are also included. The content of the proposed functions and their relationship with other functions will be examined.

Economic relations, as understood by economics, refer to the relationships between people that arise during the processes of producing, distributing, exchanging, and consuming goods. The primary and decisive relationships are those in production or production relations. Economic relations, in terms of their scope and content, are broader and richer than production relations, although they are more clearly outlined in economic literature. While production relations are studied in detail and well-established, economic relations related to distribution, exchange, and consumption are often not examined in practice.

The economic relations that arise during the process of distributing and redistributing newly created value are a component of the overall economic relations and are referred to as the distribution relations that determine the formation of population income. These relations express the objective, stable connections and interactions between the subjects involved in income formation. Their driving force consists of economic interests and property relations.

The subjects of economic relations are the population, enterprises, and the state. The population is considered as a collective of households, individuals, and specific groups.

In the economic relations regarding the formation of population income, the state operates at various levels of governance, including federal, regional, and local levels, through certain structural divisions such as the Pension Fund, Social Insurance Fund, social protection, and social security services, among others.

² Author's work

Enterprises (organizations) are economic entities that create additional value and generate income for employees in the process of value creation and distribution.

The formation of population income occurs in two stages, each corresponding to specific economic relations. In the first stage (primary distribution), economic relations arise between the population (employees) and enterprises (owners) through the creation of primary (factor) income during the process of distributing newly created value. In the second stage (redistribution), economic relations are formed between the population and the state, between groups and individuals, during the process of income redistribution, with the population not only as income recipients but also as active participants in this process.

The objects of economic relations include wages, income derived from property, income from entrepreneurial activities, social payments, and other types of income that differ according to the stages of the distribution of newly created value. The objects of economic relations are defined by the goals and economic interests of the population.

When generating income for the population, the economic relations formed by their subjects are divided into three types: socio-economic, organizational-economic, and institutional-economic (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Economic relations in the formation of population income³

Social-economic relations reflect the social essence of the economic activity of individuals in implementing their economic interests, describing the social status of the population, and are manifested in the volume and structure of their monetary income. The social component of these relations is defined by the nature and content of the relationships between participants, determining the type, composition, and volume of income, as well as the conditions and content of

³ Author's work

activities that ensure income generation. The economic component defines their relationship to production factors and their role in the creation, distribution, and redistribution of newly created value. In the formation of the population's income, ownership relations over production means give social content to economic relations.

Organizational-economic relations refer to the interactions and relationships between the subjects of these relations, the order and procedure for their implementation, the role, functions, responsibilities, obligations of the team and each employee, types of income, and the procedure for calculating them. These relations are objectively linked with the necessity of reflecting and pre-determining the content of calculations and their deadlines; establishing organizational forms of communication and relationships, regulating and managing them.

In economic theory, the system of economic relations is divided into two qualitative types: social-economic and organizational-economic, the content of which is fully disclosed in economic literature. These types of economic relations also manifest in the formation of population incomes and reflect their essence.

Institutional and economic relations are defined by the adherence to formal and informal norms and rules that determine people's behavior and the nature of their interactions during the income generation process. They also describe the relationships and interactions between the population and economic institutions: the property institute, the labor market, trade unions, banks, and others. These institutions influence the types of population income, their methods of formation, techniques, standards, and levels. These relationships emerge during the process of forming population income, affect socio-economic and organizational-economic relations, and are linked with the objective necessity of organizing interactions and interrelations between economic relations' subjects.

Conclusion

When studying household income, if we take into account the views of various economists, initially, they focused on studying income in terms of quantity. However, nowadays, the focus is shifting towards studying income in terms of quality.

The category of population income is a broad concept, in which we need to examine all forms of material values received by the population from a quantitative perspective. From this point of view, various economists have developed different theories, each providing a unique perspective, and the definition of the concept takes these differences into account.

In the formation of population income, the level of participation of economic relations is also present. Therefore, when studying it, it is essential to analyze organizational-economic relations, socio-economic relations, and institutional-economic relations separately.

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